

PAYVANDLASH VA ULARNI TURLARI TUSHUNCHASI

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Farg‘ona viloyati Oltiariq tumani
2 son kasb hunar maktabi
payvandlash asoslari fani o‘qituvchisi

Annotasiya: Maqolada payvandlash tushunchasiga ta'rif berish bilan birga, uning turlari batafsil tushuntiriladi. Bir-biridan farqli tomonlari, ijobiy va salbiy – yutuq va kamchiliklari ko'rsatishga xarakat qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Payvandlash, gaz, qurilish, tok, element, biriktirish.

Аннотация: В статье описывается понятие сварки и подробно объясняются ее виды. Сделана попытка показать разные стороны, положительные и отрицательные – достижения и недостатки.

Ключевые слова: Сварка, газ, конструкция, ток, элемент, крепление.

Abstract: The article describes the concept of welding and explains its types in detail. An attempt has been made to show different sides, positive and negative - achievements and shortcomings.

Key words: Welding, gas, design, current, element, fastening.

Metall konstruksiyalar alohida elementlarni o'zaro biriktirish natijasida yasaladi. Hozirgi vaqtda metall konstruksiyalarning elementlari ikki xil usulda biriktiriladi: qizdirib chekkalarini eritib payvandlash usullari bilan yoki sovuq holatda parmalab teshib boltlar yoki parchin mixlar yordamida.

Payvandlash usullari haqida qisqacha ma'lumot berib o'tsak. Payvandlash yo'li bilan turli xil profillardan foydalangan holda xilmaxil konstruksiyalarni

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yaratish mumkin. Payvandlash usullarini, asosan ikki guruhga bo'lish mumkin: biriktirilayotgan detallarni eritib payvandlash va qizdirib bosim bilan payvandlash. Metallarni payvandlash uchun issiqlik quvvatining manbai sifatida elektr yoyi yoki gaz alangasidan foydalaniladi. Ishlab chiqarish texnologiyasiga ko'ra payvandlashning quyidagi xillari mavjud: qo'lda payvandlash, yarim avtomatik va avtomatik usullarda payvandlash.

Metallni elektr yoyi yordamida payvandlash XIX asrning oxirida rus muhandislar N.N.Benardos va N.G.Slavyanov tomonidan kashf etilib, butun dunyoga keng tarqaldi. Elektr yoyi yordamida payvandlash quyidagicha amalga oshiriladi. Biriktiriladigan qismlarning uchlariga elektrod yaqinlashtirilganda elektr yoyi xosil bo'lib, undan katta miqdordagi issiqlik ajralib chiqadi va bu issiqlik elektrodni eritib uning qismga ko'chib o'tishiga ko'maklashadi. Qismning elektrodga yaqinlashgan joyi ham suyuqlanib eriy boshlaydi. Natijada, qismlar orasidagi bo'shliq elektrod metalli bilan to'ladi va qismlar yaxlit elementga aylanadi. Payvandlash paytida chok metaliga havodan zararli gaz moddalari aralashmasligi uchun elektrodning sirti maxsus himoyalovchi modda bilan qoplangan bo'ladi. Elektrod suyuqlanganda mazkur moddadan ko'p miqdorda gaz ajralib chiqib, chok atrofidagi havoning metallga aralashishiga to'sqinlik qiladi. Bunday tadbir ko'rilmasa, havo tarkibidagi kislorod va azot suyuq metallga qo'shilib, chokning sifatini pasaytirib yuboradi. Qurilishda ayniqsa montaj ishlarni bajarishda universalligi va noqulay bo'lgan joylarda ham payvandlash ishlarni bajarish imkoniyati borligi uchun qo'lda payvandlash usuli bilan payvandlash juda keng tarqalgan.

Utuq bo'lmagan taraflari - asosiy po'latni erish qalinligi kamligi va unumdorlikning pastligi, sababi tokning kuchi kamligida. Elektr yoyi yordamida avtomatik tarzda payvandlash Bu usulda elektr yoyini boshqarish elektrod va flyusni yetkazib berish va payvandlovchi aravachani chok bo'ylab harakatga keltirish avtomatik ravishda amalga oshiriladi. Elektr yoyi payvandlanayotgan

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buyum bilan elektrod simi orasida hosil bo'ladi. Ajralib chiqqan issiqlik ta'siri natijasida flyus qatlami ostida suyuq metall vannasi hosil bo'ladi. Bunda yoy, flyus qatlami ostida yonadi, demak payvandlash jarayoni havosiz muhitda olib boriladi. Bunday payvandlashda yuqori sifatli tekis sirtga ega bo'lgan kumush rangli payvand chok hosil bo'ladi; po'lat eritmasi juda toza va sifatli chiqadi. Ishlatiladigan katta kuchli tok (600-1200 A) va eritilgan po'latning issiqligini saqlash imkoniyati borligi sababli elementlar birikmasi juda chuqur va mustahkam xamda unumli bo'ladi. Kamchiligi – tik va shift holatda hamda noqulay bo'lgan joyda bu usul bilan payvandlashni bajarish imkoniyati yo'qligi. Elektroshlak usuli bilan payvandlash Bu usul ayniqsa tik bo'lgan tutashish choklarini payvandlash bajarishda avtomat mexanizmlar yordamida bajariladi. Elektroshlak usuli, payvandlanadigan elementlarning qalinligi 20mm dan ortiq bo'lganda qo'llaniladi. Elementlarning bir biriga biriktirilishi toza sim orqali va eritilgan shlak ostida o'tadi. SHu usul bilan bajariladigan choklar juda sifatli, toza va mustahkam bo'lib chiqadi. Himoyalovchi gazlar muhitida payvandlash Payvandlashning bu usuli suyuqlanuvchi elektrod yordamida yarim avtomatik tarzda bajariladi, payvandlovchi kallakka qayishqoq shlang orqali elektrod va karbonat angidridi gazi uzatiladi. Karbonat angidridi gazi yoyning yonish doirasidan havoni siqib chiqarib, suyuqlangan metalni kislorod va azot ta'siridan himoya qiladi. CHoklar sifatli chiqadi faqat tashqi ko'rinishi notekis bo'ladi. Avtomatik usul bilan bajarishga qaraganda, unumdorligi 15-20% gacha yuqoriroq. Bu usul bilan payvandlashning kamchiliklari: po'latdagi uglerod ko'payishining havfi bor, kallakni sovitish uchun suv bo'lishi sharti, ishchilarni ham yoyni ham gazni ta'siridan asrash kerakligi.

Gaz alangasida payvandlash. Payvandlashning ushbu usulida biriktiriladigan elementlar yonuvchi gazlar (asetilen, tabiiy gaz, kerosin va benzin bug'lari) yordamida qizdirilib ularning payvandlanadigan joyi suyuqlangandan keyin,

yonayotgan alangaga metall sim kiritiladi. Bu sim asosiy elementlarni qirralaridagi metali bilan birga suyuqlanib, bir butun yaxlit birikma hosil qiladi.

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